

Software module based on lifetime analysis for a predictive maintenance decision-support system

Manuel Vaamonde-Rivas

Instituto Tecnológico de Matemática Industrial (ITMATI)

Abelardo Monsalve-Cobis

Instituto Tecnológico de Matemática Industrial (ITMATI)

Juan Carlos Pardo-Fernández,

Universidade de Vigo and

Instituto Tecnológico de Matemática Industrial (ITMATI)

Jacobo de Uña-Álvarez,

Universidade de Vigo and

Instituto Tecnológico de Matemática Industrial (ITMATI)

Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to introduce a software module based on lifetime analysis to provide useful information in the decision making of preventive maintenance tasks. The specific role of this software is to predict future values of a condition monitoring variable, to evaluate the future probability of failure, and to report information on the remaining lifetime of the targeted component and thus to contribute to the decision-making in the preventive maintenance tasks.

Design/methodology/approach: The software module is integrated by two main sub-modules that are fed by historical data to estimate the selected statistical models, which are then used to perform prediction from the current data available. Finally, the outcomes of the modules are sent to the central system, where the decision-making process is accomplished.

Findings: The information provided by the software comprises, estimates of the parameters of the underlying lifetime model and prediction of the failure probability and the residual lifetime of a target device of a machine.

Practical implications: Increase availability and maintainability.

Social implications: Reduction failure-related accidents, Reduction of energy consumption.

Originality/value: This software module can be used and integrated to any central system to predict the failure probability and generating report to preventive maintenance in real-time by permanent executing of the online submodule.

Keywords: Accelerated failure time model, Weibull distribution, Weibull regression models, Reliability.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, the manufacturing industry is subdued to various factors that directly influence its production capacity and the profitability of this activity. Some of these factors are related to efficient and low-cost production processes, which are evolving under the paradigm of Industry 4.0 or smart manufacturing. The fourth industrial revolution has been reshaping the industrial manufacturing scenario by combining information technologies as Big Data and Cloud Computing with robotics and physical machinery, increasing the digitalization of industrial processes. The

core ideas and challenges of Industry 4.0 can be found in [Saucedo-Martínez et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Pereira & Romero \(2017\)](#).

Knowing an industrial environment and its ambient conditions is highly important to make intelligent decisions over machinery. Compared with other fields not connected to production, the application of digitalization and data analysis is less advanced in the industry. This is partially due to the fact that in industrial settings knowledge needs to be retrieved by sensors installed on machines, and this is still an ongoing process. Sensors allow better decisions to be taken, and this positively impacts efficiency. The industrial progress is, then, tied to the evolution of sensors and instrumentation, which can even be seen as a driving force ([Schütze et al. \(2018\)](#)). Taking advantage of new technologies on smart sensing makes possible the construction of a Internet of Things network, which can be used as the cornerstone for a predictive maintenance platform.

Over the last years the most popular maintenance solution was preventive maintenance, which schedules periodic maintenances in order to detect failures or decreases in performance before they happen. However, this approach is not the most cost-efficient, as the cost introduced by unnecessary stoppages needs to be taken into account. In addition, if between maintenances machines are not being monitored, unexpected failures can occur, adding another limitation to this type of maintenance. Being able to intervene just when needed would add great value to the maintenance strategy. This is the goal of predictive maintenance ([Selcuk \(2016\)](#)), where the condition of machine components is estimated through data retrieved by sensors and decisions are taken accordingly. Compared with preventive maintenance, the predictive approach is more suited to the new Industry 4.0 environment. The growing tendency of predictive maintenance can be seen at [Zonta et al. \(2020\)](#).

This document introduces a software module based on lifetime analysis which can provide information regarding the reliability of the equipment, so predictive maintenance-based decisions can be taken. This software, hereinafter referred to as the LTA, is integrated into a large central system called PreCoM. PreCoM is a three-year Industry 4.0 project, funded by the Horizon 2020 Programme (EU-H2020-FOF-09, 2017-2020), which aims to implement and validate a predictive maintenance decision support system. The system, based on predictive maintenance, is designed to predict damage development in order to intervene before a failure occurs, providing guidance to carry out repairs at the lowest possible cost and time. PreCoM consists of four main subsystems: a *detection module*, that is a real-time data acquisition platform; an *Artificial Intelligence module*, that applies data-based models which are used to predict the future condition of a component; a *production planning module*, which optimizes production scheduling; and finally, the *user interface module*, based on Augmented Reality.

The LTA is part of the Artificial Intelligence module and aims to estimate relevant quantities like the mean residual lifetime (MRL) and the probability of failure over a period. The LTA software integrates lifetime data analysis techniques (see, for example, [Lawless \(2011\)](#)) in order to apply them to historical data, enabling the identification of the most suitable model and its target parameters, depending on working conditions. These parameters can report key information for describing the machine/component condition and predict its possible development in the future.

The analysis of lifetime data comprises statistical models widely studied for the characterization of reliability.

Lifetime data analysis has been widely used and studied in the field of manufacturing industry. This is reflected in the extensive literature on this subject: [Blischke & Murthy \(2003\)](#), [Kenett & Zacks \(2014\)](#), [Kenett & Zacks \(2013\)](#), [Rausand & Hoyland \(2013\)](#), [Lazzaroni et al. \(2011\)](#), among others. The statistical model selected for the LTA software to estimate the reliability function is the Weibull model. This is one of the most used distributions in the context of reliability in industry (see, for example, [Lai et al. \(2004\)](#), [Elmahdy & Aboutahoun \(2013\)](#), or [Smith \(1991\)](#)). Parametric approaches, as the Weibull model, can be preferred over a non-parametric one because they can offer a wider range of interpretable results. It was selected after the studies performed over the PreCoM data as it provided a good fit.

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2, a brief description of the statistical methodology used in the development of the proposal. Section 3 describes the main features of the LTA software. The fourth section depicts a real data application of LTA. Finally, some conclusions are given in Section 5.

2 Lifetime data analysis

The main goal of Lifetime data analysis (LTA) in PreCoM Project is to estimate the probability distribution of the remaining operation time of the targeted machine/component. This probability distribution allows us to calculate relevant parameters such as the mean residual lifetime, future probabilities of failure or stoppage, and specific quantiles of the residual life. The estimation of such parameters will be performed through proper statistical methods for the analysis of lifetimes or failure data (Kalbfleisch & Prentice (2011)). These methods are briefly outlined now.

Analysis of failure time data deals with the problem of studying the time until a failure or event of interest happens. For instance, vibration or temperature overtaking an established threshold may indicate the event of failure.

In what follows, T denotes a nonnegative random variable representing the failure time of an individual from a homogeneous population for simplicity in the exposition. In our practical scenarios, the distribution of T may depend on particular machine/component characteristics, working conditions, manufactured product type, etc., and these covariates will be taken into account. How to include the covariates in the model will be explained too.

The probability distribution of T can be specified in many ways, four of which are especially useful: the reliability (or survival) function, the probability density function, the failure rate (or hazard) function and the expected residual life at time t . In the following sections we describe them briefly.

2.1 The reliability function

The probability that T exceeds a value t in its range defines the reliability (or survival) function. That is,

$$R(t) = \mathbb{P}(T > t) = 1 - F(t), \quad 0 < t < \infty, \quad (1)$$

where F represents the distribution function of T , $F(t) = \mathbb{P}(T \leq t)$. It is verified that R is a continuous and decreasing monotone function satisfying $R(0) = 1$ and $R(\infty) = 0$. In addition, the p -quantile with $0 < p < 1$ of the distribution of T is defined as the value t_p verifying $F(t_p) = \mathbb{P}(T \leq t_p) = p$, or equivalently, $t_p = F^{-1}(p)$, where F^{-1} denotes the inverse function of F . Quantiles may be seen as cutpoints dividing the range of a probability distribution according to the value of p that may be used to decide when maintenance tasks must be carried out too. Depending on values of p , the decision of maintenance will be more conservative or more risky. The density function can be obtained from the distribution function F as its derivative:

$$f(t) = \frac{dF(t)}{dt} = F'(t)$$

The *failure rate* (or hazard) function h specifies the instantaneous rate at which a failure occurs at time t . It is satisfied that $h(t) = f(t)/R(t)$. Now integrating, we obtain the *cumulative failure rate* function H :

$$H(t) = \int_{[0,t]} h(u)du = -\log(1 - F(t))$$

Decreasing hazard functions appear when the probability of failure is high at early stages. Such a decreasing shape may be provoked by the existence of defective components in the production. Constant hazard functions are common when failures are due to random phenomena like accidents. Finally, increasing hazard functions appear in the presence of wear in the component or machine of interest.

2.2 Mean residual lifetime (MRL)

In reliability studies, the mean residual life or residual life expectancy is an important characteristic of the model. So, the expected residual life at time t is another representation of the failure time distribution that may be useful in the predictive maintenance. It is defined as the conditional expectation:

$$r(t) = \mathbb{E}(T - t \mid T \geq t) = \frac{\int_{[t, \infty]} R(u) du}{R(t)} \quad (2)$$

where $R(\cdot)$ is the reliability function given in (1). The mean residual life is the expected remaining lifetime of the component given that it has not failed up to time t .

For location-scale based parametric distributions (exponential, Weibull, lognormal), we denote the location parameter by μ and the scale by σ . Note that using (2), the mean life, $\mu = r(0)$, is the total area under reliability curve

$$\mu = \mathbb{E}(T) = \int_{[0, \infty]} R(u) du.$$

For mean residual life, the confidence intervals are obtained by delta method (see Meeker & Escobar (1998)). In order to obtain prediction of future random quantities, in particular, predictions intervals for the mean residual life, expression (2) and the methods to construct predictions intervals in (Meeker & Escobar (1998) p. 289-298) are taken into account. In reliability analysis, the *conditional probability of failure* (also called *failure probability n-ahead*) in the interval $(t, t + \Delta t)$, given being alive at time t , is given by

$$\mathbb{P}(T - t < \Delta t \mid T > t) = \mathbb{P}(t < T < t + \Delta t \mid T > t) = \frac{R(t) - R(t + \Delta t)}{R(t)} = 1 - \frac{R(t + \Delta t)}{R(t)},$$

where Δt denotes the length of the period over which this probability is calculated. It is the probability of failure in an upcoming period of interest if a failure has not occurred yet. If the conditional probability of failure of a given machine or component is unusually high, it could be a reason to intervene propitiously, thereby preempting the consequences of a failure in the production while avoiding waste of resources and unnecessary downtime on components where failure is not imminent. The confidence bands for the conditional probability or failure probability n -ahead can be obtained by applying the delta method (see Meeker & Escobar (1998))

In the following Section we specify all the aforementioned important functions for the Weibull model, which is one of the most widely used parametric models for the analysis of lifetime data.

2.3 The Weibull distribution model

Certain parametric models have been used in the literature devoted to failure time data. Exponential or Weibull distributions Abernethy (2006) are the most commonly used models for T . These distributions admit closed expressions for tail area probabilities and, therefore, simple formulas for reliability and failure rate functions. Since the Exponential model is a particular case of the Weibull distribution, we describe only the latter of these two distributions.

The random variable T follows a Weibull distribution with scale parameter $a > 0$ and shape parameter $b > 0$, and it is denoted by $T \sim Weibull(a, b)$, if its density function is

$$f(t) = ab(at)^{b-1} \exp\left\{-(at)^b\right\}, \quad t > 0.$$

In this case, $F(t) = 1 - \exp\left\{-(at)^b\right\}$ and therefore the reliability function is given by $R(t) = \exp\left\{-(at)^b\right\}$.

The failure rate function can be written as $h(t) = ab(at)^{b-1}$. Several failure rate functions can be obtained according to the values of the parameter b . If $b < 1$, the hazard function h is

a decreasing function. If $b > 1$ then h is an increasing function. Finally, if $b = 1$, the hazard function is constant. In this last case, the Weibull distribution reduces to the Exponential.

In addition, the p -quantile of the Weibull distribution is given by the expression $t_p = (1/a)[- \log(1 - p)]^{1/b}$. The maintenance decision could be more conservative or risky depending on the selected percentile.

The *mean residual life* function of the Weibull model equals

$$r(t) = \frac{\Gamma(1/b; (ta)^b)}{(ab \exp\{-(at)^b\})}$$

where $\Gamma(s; t) = \int_{[t, \infty]} u^{s-1} e^{-u} du$ is the incomplete Gamma function. Thus, the mean residual life can be easily evaluated given the parameters a and b .

In practical scenarios, the time to failure or stoppage may depend on the machine working conditions, product type and other covariates. The usual Weibull regression model is the one specifying that the scale parameter is a certain transformation (such as the exponential transform) of a linear predictor $a(x) = \exp(\beta'x)$ say, where x denotes the vector of available covariates (product being manufactured, working conditions, machine characteristics, etc.) and β' denotes the transposed vector of regression coefficients to be estimated from the failure time data.

The Weibull regression model also belongs to the family of accelerated failure time (AFT) models. Under this viewpoint, $\exp(\beta'x)$ is interpreted as a factor which accelerates time leading to an earlier (if the factor is > 1) or later (if < 1) failure of the device.

For example, let A and B be two products manufactured by a specific machine, and assume that the covariate vector x reduces to the product indicator. Let $S_A(t)$ and $S_B(t)$ denote the reliability functions for a critical component when A and B are manufactured, respectively. It could be natural to assume, according the expert-knowledge, that

$$S_A(t) = S_B(kt)$$

where $k > 0$ is the acceleration factor. In other words, this model implies that aging rate of the products A is k times as much as that of product B .

The AFT model is special in the field of reliability analysis in that it is a fully parametric model. This provides power to make certain inferences such as the estimation of tail probabilities that would be difficult in a non-parametric or semi-parametric framework. The structure of AFT models is as follows. For a vector of failure times, T , given a data matrix X (covariates matrix), the AFT model defines the relationship of reliability function for each failure time, $t \in T$, $R(t|X)$ and the covariates as

$$R(t|X) = R_0(t \exp(\beta'X)),$$

where R_0 is the baseline reliability function and β' is a vector of regression coefficients. The relationship between covariates and the failure time can be also illustrated as the following linear expression:

$$\log(T) = \mu + \theta'X + \sigma\varepsilon,$$

where μ is the slope, $\sigma > 0$, $\theta = -\beta$ and ε follows the smallest extreme value distribution.

One peculiar feature often present in the lifetime models is *censoring*. Broadly speaking, censoring occurs when the actual values of some lifetimes are not known. For instance, due to some particular issues in the data generating process, for some lifetimes we might just know that they exceed a certain value (right censoring) or they belong to a certain interval (interval censoring). More precisely, in the right censoring scheme, only the minimum of the lifetime of interest, T , and the censoring time, C , is observable and thus the available data would come from the pair (Y, δ) , where $Y = \min\{T, C\}$ and $\delta = I(T \leq C)$, where $I(\cdot)$ is the indicator function.

3 LTA software module

LTA implements statistical lifetime analysis models for the assessment of the future conditions of machine components. The specific role of this software is to estimate the reliability function of the target component, so then probabilities of failure and mean residual life can be computed. This software module is designed to carry out lifetime analysis process in two parts: *offline* and *online*. The *offline* part (LTA offline) is responsible for fitting the best model. Then it is stored on a fixed repository. The *online* part (LTA online) is continuously working, checking the latest available data, and, by using the output of the offline part, generates predictions of the component remaining in-service lifetime.

A summary of the whole execution process of the module is displayed in Figure 1. It also highlights the integration within the PreCoM system, which is done mainly by the connection with the Big Data services at the Cloud and the PreCoM Brain, which manages all the system. The module is located at Docker containers, which are a standard unit of software that is isolated from the rest of the system and can run a process reliably and quickly.

The code of LTA has been developed in R language (R Core Team (2019)) and can be run automatically without user intervention, while still allowing manual inputs if needed. R is a programming language and free software environment for statistical computing and graphics. The R language is widely used among statisticians, programmers and data miners for developing statistical software and data analysis. R functionality is accessible from several scripting programming languages such as *Python*, *Perl*, and *Ruby*. Interfaces to other high-level programming languages, like *Java* and *C*, are available as well. Because of this, the LTA software can be integrated easily in other programming structures as well.

3.1 LTA offline

The offline module is the first part of the software. There is no fixed recommendation on how often to execute it, as it strictly depends on the case. Nevertheless, if the conditions over the target component have been modified, an update would be recommended so the fitted model captures the latest behavior more precisely. Then, if no expert advice is available, a good rule-of-thumb could be updating the model whenever there is a change on production and/or the activity of the machine and its components. In order to do this, the advice would be to fit the model with historical data that resembles the new conditions of the machine. For example, if the machine has been producing a material for a month, a different material the next month, and then it continues producing the first material, the recommendation would be to use the data from the first month to fit the model that will be used during the third month. In many cases a model could be stored for each production conditions under which the machine usually works, so when there is a change, a previously fitted model is ready to be used.

If the former process cannot be replicated because the new conditions are completely new, then the old model would be used while data representing the new conditions are generated. The waiting time before fitting the model here depends on the use case. If the target components has a lifetime of weeks, then a long period is needed to generate enough data of component replacement. However, if the target component had a lifetime of hours, a few days would be sufficient to generate data.

This module obtains the data from the PreCoM Cloud by using an application programming interface (API). The three main arguments needed for LTA offline module are: the name of the variable or target parameter, the date range that is used to fit the model, and a code indicating the use case.

At production, the module would be executed from console or from other software, but an additional standalone web application was developed based on Shiny R package (Chang et al. (2020)). Figure 2 shows a screenshot of the offline module the Shiny app. The interface allows the user to select the initial and final date (in the time zone UTC) and the variable that defines

Figure 1. Diagram representing the integration of the LTA software module within the PreCoM system.

Figure 2. Offline module app.

the event (top left). Once the model is fitted a summary table of the statistical model (top right) and a graph of the reliability function (bottom) is displayed.

3.2 LTA online

The online part of the LTA software is the most important part of the computational strategy proposed in this paper. This submodule has the task of taking the information of the model estimated by the offline part to analyze the most recent data to evaluate the current state of the target component. The main output of the module is a .CSV table. This table is composed by the predictions of mean residual life and failure probabilities with alarm levels obtained from these probabilities. The levels of these alarms go from 0 to 4:

- **0:** No damage (Failure probability 0 to 0.05).
- **1:** No serious damage, await (Failure probability 0.05 to 0.15).
- **2:** Probable damage during development, await (Failure probability 0.15 to 0.3).
- **3:** Examine the device whenever you can (Failure probability 0.3 to 0.6).
- **4:** Maintenance should be planned (Failure probability 0.6 to 1).

As for the offline part, the standalone Shiny app can illustrate the usage of the software. Figure 3 show screenshots the online part with a probability of failure graphical output.

4 Applications

The PreCoM project has three industrial partners that provide different machines with different conditions where the system and its modules can be tested. In this section, two LTA module applications, corresponding with two of these industrial demonstrators, will be presented.

Figure 3. Online module app.

4.1 Case study 1: Continuous Production

The demo-company for the first case is Gomà-Camps. This company is devoted to the manufacturing, transformation and sale of tissue paper and other related solutions. It has paper machines equipped with creping systems by Lantier, another PreCoM partner, for the production of 100% virgin cellulose tissue and recycled tissue, with a total capacity over 60,000 metric ton/per year. The critical component (target parameter) identified for this use case is the *creping blade* (see Figure, 4 left), that separates the paper from the yankee drying cylinder (see Figure, 4 right). In this sense, the failure event is defined as the replacement of the creping blade.

Figure 4. Blade holder (left) and creping doctor and yankee cylinder (right) at Gomà-Camps.

For confidentiality reasons we will refer to data with time units, instead of seconds, minutes or days. A time unit was chosen as the the maximum time of usage of the creping blade according to the factory. This information is confirmed by the data: the 84.1% of the replacements occurred within the limit of a time unit. The Weibull model fitted to the time-to-failure data reported

a scale parameter $a = 1.026$ and shape parameter $b = 1.327$ (see Table I). This gives mean replacement time for the creeping blade of 0.9436 time units.

	est	Lower-95%	Upper-95%	se
a(scale)	1.026	0.777	1.355	0.146
b(shape)	1.327	1.006	1.750	0.187

N = 31, Events: 31, Censored: 0
Total time at risk: 29.379
Log-likelihood = -27.6041, df = 2
AIC = 59.2080

Table I. Summary of fitted Weibull model.

For illustration and validation purposes, we depict in Figure 5 the nonparametric Kaplan-Meier estimator of the reliability together with the Weibull fit. Both curves are in good agreement, supporting the choice of the Weibull model. In Figure 6, the evaluation of the mean residual time to failure along 2 time units of operation (left panel) and the failure probability 0.2 time units ahead depending on the current operation time (right panel) are displayed. The shape parameter is greater than one, indicating an increasing hazard; so the remaining expected lifetime of the creeping blade decreases as time advances, while the probability of failure increases. This behaviour can be seen in Figure 5, even if it is slight, specially on the probability of failure graph. One time unit is a relatively small operation time for the blade, so, since the probability is conditional that the blade has been in-service up to the time for which is computed, the resulting probabilities are small.

Figure 5. Kaplan-Meier reliability function with 95% pointwise confidence band (black) together with estimated Weibull reliability (red). Gomà-Camps use case.

Table II shows an execution of LTA online with a frequency of 0.2 time units. The mean residual life is, as the probability of failure, conditional that the blade has been in-service up to the time for when it is computed. This means that, while the estimated lifetime of the component is 0.94 time units, if it is undamaged at that operation time, the expected remaining time can be high (over 0.5 time units according to the results). The alarm level for this execution increases when the estimated lifetime of the component is reached.

Figure 6. Left: Weibull-based mean residual lifetime with 95% confidence (blue) and prediction (red) bands. Right: failure probability 0.2 time units ahead with 95% confidence bands. Gomà-Camps use case.

Operation time	Failure probability	Mean residual lifetime	Warning level
0.0	0.108	0.944	1
0.2	0.158	0.844	2
0.4	0.185	0.784	2
0.6	0.204	0.739	2
0.8	0.219	0.704	2
1.0	0.232	0.674	2
1.2	0.244	0.650	2
1.4	0.254	0.628	3
1.6	0.263	0.609	3
1.8	0.271	0.592	3
2.0	0.279	0.577	3

Table II. Execution of LTA online with a frequency of 0.2 time units. Gomà-Camps use case.

4.2 Case study 2: Low Volume Production

The second demo-company considered in this paper is Sakana. This company is specialized on manufacturing large metal components for windmills, with experience in milling and drilling tools. Soraluze is a machine tool builder oriented towards milling solutions. Both of them are involved at this use case as part of the PreCoM project.

The Sakana factory manufactures components for wind turbines under a completely automated production-scheme. Figure 7 left shows the FXR milling machine (Soraluze’s machine) installed at Sakana. It can operate with multiple head tools, fitting different tasks and products. The target component for LTA at PreCoM is the *cutting tool*, designated for piercing operations. The machine is almost exclusively dedicated to the manufacturing of hubs of the wind turbine. The hub is a complicated piece that requires high precision machining in piercing operations and high power and cutting speed capability in the rest of the operations (see Figure 7 right).

As mentioned, the application of the LTA module requires the definition of a well-specified event. In this case, the considered event was an abnormal vibration. Higher vibration of tools are often related with their degradation. Abnormal (high) vibration levels were identified from historical data at Sakana by means of outlier detection techniques. Specifically, the mean vi-

Figure 7. Left: Soraluce FXR milling-boring machine installed at Sakana. Right: spindle head at Sakana machining the hub of a wind turbine.

Figure 8. Standardized mean vibration levels for 20 machined hubs and outliers (abnormal vibration levels, red points at left plot) detected by means of the rule “ $> q_{0.75} + 1.5 \cdot IQR$ ” (top points at the right plot). Sakana use case.

bration levels registered by each machine piercing action were standardized (to take vibration heterogeneity into account), and then the usual rule “ $> q_{0.75} + 1.5 \cdot IQR$ ” (more than three 1.5 times the inter-quartile range above the 75% percentile) was applied to the standardized data. See Figures 8 and 9 for illustration. Some values are not displayed at the axis due to confidentiality issues. Time-to-failure was defined as the number piercing actions up to abnormal vibration of the spindle head. For example, if for a certain hub an abnormal vibration occurs only at action $k = 6$, there are two resulting failure times: an uncensored failure time of value 6 and a censored failure time of value $N - 6$, where N is the total number of piercing actions by hub (hubs without abnormal vibrations report censored failure times with value N). A Weibull model was finally fitted to these historical data, which corresponds to 20 drilling cycles which took place over the year 2019. Figure 9 displays the detection boundary obtained from this data.

Vibration levels were normal for 13 out of the 20 machined hubs (65.5% of the hubs). The number of piercing actions reporting abnormal vibration was 14 (0.5% of the 2772 piercing actions). The number of outliers for each machined hub ranged between 0 and 5.

The Weibull model fitted to the time-to-failure data (number of piercing actions until next abnormal vibration) reported a scale parameter $a = 298.631$ and shape parameter $b = 0.6259$

Figure 9. Vibration spectrum for two different hubs (black and grey lines) and detection boundary computed from the historical data (20 machined hubs, red dashed line). Abnormal vibration levels are indicated by red circles. Sakana use case.

	est	Lower-95%	Upper-95%	se
a(scale)	298	109.056	817.753	153.486
b(shape)	0.626	0.390	1.004	0.151
N = 35, Events: 14, Censored: 21				
Total time at risk: 2772				
Log-likelihood = -85.76423, df = 2				
AIC = 175.5285				

Table III. Summary of fitted Weibull model. Sakana use case.

(see Table III). This gives an average number of piercing actions until next failure of 426.

A graphical validation of the model was performed by comparing the Weibull reliability function with the Kaplan-Meier estimator. The two estimators were in clear agreement (see Figure 10).

We have computed $r(t)$ for $N = 132$ by using the estimated Weibull model. In this case, $r(t)$ represents the mean remaining number of piercing actions up to the next failure. These values are reported in Figure 11, left; and probability of failure 10 actions ahead, right. The shape parameter of the model is lower than 1, indicating a decreasing hazard. In other words, a failure is expected to happen at the beginning of the lifetime of the component (early *infant mortality* failure), being long-lived when it does not happen. This is coherent with the graphs in Figure 11. The explanation for this behaviour could be related to damage on tools reaching the end of its lifespan and calibration issues for new tools. The cutting tool has a slow degradation, so when it is in-service the probability of damage on the component is low, and so are the produced vibrations.

In Table IV, the results of two executions of the online LTA module are displayed. Specifically, the probability of failure ten actions ahead is provided, together with the corresponding warning levels. This information is dynamically updated along the piercing procedure. Left part of Table IV refers to the production of a new hub and, therefore, the first piercing action is labelled as 1. On the contrary, the right-hand part of Table IV corresponds to an execution just after piercing action 99, where an abnormal vibration level (event) occurred. In the latter case, in

Figure 10. Kaplan-Meier reliability function with 95% pointwise confidence band (orange dotted lines) together with estimated Weibull reliability (red line) and pointwise confidence band (blue dashed lines). Sakana use case.

Figure 11. Left: Weibull-based mean number of remaining piercing actions up to next failure and 95% pointwise confidence and predictions bands (blue and red dashed lines respectively). Right: probability of failure 10 actions ahead. Sakana use case.

which a failure during the milling of the hub took place, the alarm levels are higher, informing the operator that he/she should stay vigilant in order to detect any abnormal behaviour of the piercing machine.

5 Conclusions

In this document, the LTA software module has been presented. It constitutes a computational tool for lifetime analysis model into the PreCoM system. The software has been described and illustrated with real examples in industrial settings.

Piercing actions	Failure probability 10 actions ahead	Warning level	Piercing actions	Failure probability 10 actions ahead	Warning level
1	0.171	2	100	0.197	2
2	0.156	2	101	0.185	2
3	0.146	1	102	0.177	2
4	0.138	1	103	0.170	2
5	0.132	1	104	0.164	2
6	0.127	1	105	0.160	2
7	0.122	1	106	0.155	2
8	0.118	1	107	0.152	2
9	0.144	1	108	0.148	1
10	0.111	1	109	0.145	1
11	0.108	1	110	0.143	1
12	0.106	1	111	0.140	1
13	0.103	1	112	0.138	1
14	0.101	1	113	0.136	1
15	0.099	1	114	0.134	1
16	0.097	1	115	0.132	1

Table IV. Failure probabilities 10 actions ahead of two executions of LTA online module. Left: execution performed at the beginning of the piercing cycle over a hub. Right: execution performed just after an abnormal vibration (event) that occurred at piercing action 99 at that hub. Sakana use case.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all our partners at the PreCoM project, as without them our work would not have been possible: Linnéuniversitetet, E-maintenance Sweden AB, Paragon, Savvy Data Systems SL, Vertech Group, Bosch Rexroth AG, Soraluece S. Coop., Sakana S. Coop., Overbeck GMBH, Spinea SRO, Gomà-Camps Sociedad Anónima, Lantier SL, Ideko S. Coop., Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives, Technische Universität München and Technische Universität Chemnitz.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 768575.

References

- Abernethy, R. (2006), *The New Weibull Handbook: Reliability & Statistical Analysis for Predicting Life, Safety, Risk, Support Costs, Failures, and Forecasting Warranty Claims*, 5th edn, Florida.
- Blischke, W. & Murthy, D. (2003), *Case Studies in Reliability and Maintenance*, Wiley.
- Chang, W., Cheng, J., Allaire, J., Xie, Y. & McPherson, J. (2020), *shiny: Web Application Framework for R*. R package version 1.5.0.
URL: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=shiny>
- Elmahdy, E. & Aboutahoun, A. (2013), 'A new approach for parameter estimation of finite weibull mixture distributions for reliability modeling', *Applied Mathematical Modelling* (37), 1800–1810.
- Kalbfleisch, J. & Prentice, R. (2011), *The Statistical Analysis of Failure Time Data*, 2nd edn, Wiley, New York.

- Kenett, R. & Zacks, S. (2013), *Reliability Physics and Engineering. Time-to-Failure Modeling*, 2nd edn, Springer.
- Kenett, R. & Zacks, S. (2014), *Modern Industrial Statistics with applications in R, MINITAB and JMP*, Wiley.
- Lai, C., Zhang, L. & Xie, M. (2004), ‘Mean residual life and other properties of weibull related bathtub shape’, *International Journal of Reliability, Quality and Safety Engineering* **11**(2), 113–132.
- Lawless, J. (2011), *Statistical Models and Methods for Lifetime Data*, 2nd edn, Wiley & Sons.
- Lazzaroni, M., Cristaldi, L., Peretto, L., Rinaldi, P. & Catelani, M. (2011), *Reliability Engineering Basic Concepts and Applications in ICT*, Springer.
- Meeker, W. & Escobar, L. (1998), *Statistical Methods for Reliability Data*, Wiley.
- Pereira, A. & Romero, F. (2017), ‘A review of the meanings and the implications of the industry 4.0 concept’, *Procedia Manufacturing* **13**, 1206–1214. Manufacturing Engineering Society International Conference 2017, MESIC 2017, 28-30 June 2017, Vigo (Pontevedra), Spain.
URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2351978917306649>
- R Core Team (2019), *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.
URL: <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Rausand, M. & Hoyland, A. (2013), *System Reliability Theory. Models, Statistical Methods, and Applications*, Springer.
- Saucedo-Martínez, J., Pérez-Lara, M., Marmolejo-Saucedo, J., Salais-Fierro, T. & Vasant, P. (2018), ‘Industry 4.0 framework for management and operations: a review’, *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing* **9**, 789–801.
- Schütze, A., Helwig, N. & Schneider, T. (2018), ‘Sensors 4.0 – smart sensors and measurement technology enable industry 4.0’, *Journal of Sensors and Sensor Systems* **7**(1), 359–371.
URL: <https://search.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/sensors-4-0-smart-measurement-technology-enable/docview/2151113867/se-2?accountid=17253>
- Selcuk, S. (2016), ‘Predictive maintenance, its implementation and latest trends’, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part B: Journal of Engineering Manufacture* **231**(9), 1670–1679.
- Smith, R. (1991), ‘Weibull regression models for reliability data’, *Reliability Engineering and System Safety* **34**(1), 55–76.
- Zonta, T., da Costa, C. A., da Rosa Righi, R., de Lima, M. J., da Trindade, E. S. & Li, G. P. (2020), ‘Predictive maintenance in the industry 4.0: A systematic literature review’, *Computers and Industrial Engineering* **150**, 106889.
URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360835220305787>

MANUEL VAAMONDE-RIVAS. *E-mail address:* manuel.vaamonde.rivas@usc.es

ABELARDO MONSALVE-COBIS. *E-mail address:* amonsalve@uvigo.es

JUAN CARLOS PARDO-FERNÁNDEZ. *E-mail address:* juancp@uvigo.es

JACOBO DE UÑA-ÁLVAREZ. *E-mail address:* jacobo@uvigo.es